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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HEALTH DYNAMICS (OSCILLATING BRAIN IN VACILLATING MILIEU)

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'The illiterate of the 21st century will not be those who cannot read or write, But, those who cannot learn, unlearn, and relearn'.

..... Alvin Toffler

Abstract

Alvin Toffler had propounded a 'First Wave'; agrarian revolution, a 'Second Wave'; industrial revolution and a 'Third Wave'; Information revolution ('neuron' in a third-wave information age in which linked computer databases are like a neural network). Present 21st Century has been engulfed by the forces of Artificial Intelligence (hereafter, AI); seen, unseen, felt, not felt, perceived and not perceives. The depth, span, magnitude, velocity and speed are immense. In such a scenario, how is the Oscillating Brain going to act and react in an air of Vacillating AI Milieu? Will brain be influenced by the Vacillating AI Milieu? Will AI be impacted by the Oscillating Brain? Can we fit a biological brain into a machine via AL pathways? Can we fit in a machine into the brain (Musk - Model)? The methodology adopted is based on the work '*The Singularity Is Near*' by Ray Kurzweil (2005). This paper discusses these issues with reflections from movies ('A Beautiful Mind'; 2001, 'Lucy'; 2014 and Enthiran / Machine; 2010). Conclusions lead to the state that AI is short – lived with a shelf - life and biological brain will reign supreme.

Keywords: oscillating brain, vacillating ai and '*singularity is near*'

'I do not think there is any thrill that can go through the human heart like that felt by the inventor as he sees some creation of the brain unfolding to success'.

..... Nikola Tesla

Introduction

Predicting the future of AI, Kurzweil in his seminal work titled 'The Singularity Is Near: When Humans Transcend Biology', has propounded that humanity stands on the cusp of a revolution that would experience a 'technological tectonics' leading to a well – calibrated algorithm of architectural destiny. This is based on the concept of 'Law of Accelerating

Returns'. Bringing on board 'Technological Intelligence' and 'Human Intelligence', the study concluded that 'Technological Intelligence' would be infinitely omnipotent but there would arrive a point wherein 'Technological Intelligence' and 'Human Intelligence' would merge to depict a 'Singularity'. A machine brain will only function based on the commands fed by a biological brain via the pre - fed

computer programming and soft wares. The questions that we raise here is; where is the element and component of 'Intellect'; 'The Power of the Infinite Mind'? Will a wired brain of the machine (or, biological brain) be able to discharge the functions of a biological brain (or, machine brain)? Can a machine brain exhibit biological left brain's logical, organized thinking set of commands or right brain's emotional and creative thinking choices? Can a machine replace the neurons of human brain? Can a machine brain 'think out of the box'? As a corollary, this paper purports that AI is 'Synthetic' or 'Fabricated' Intelligence (and not 'intellect').

Mankind: Slave of AI

Artificial is artificial. But, one wonders how Natural Language Processing (NLP) is 'Natural' in a milieu of 'artificial'? Why can't it be connoted as Artificial Language Processing (ALP)? In the 'game' of Human - Machine Interface and Brain - Machine Interface, mankind is now so dependent on Generative Pre-trained Transformers (GPT) like Chat GPT, Google Bard, and Microsoft Bing and Copilot, that one can safely connote them as 'Slave of AI'. Gone are the days of COBOL, PASCAL, FORTRAN, LOTUS, Floppy Disks, Compact Discs, Pen Drives, and Thumb Drives. Gone are the days of physical financial transactions (Bank, Ticket Windows, and Paper Prints). AI today has occupied a 'protoplasmic' graph with the computer acting as the 'Cyber Mitochondria'. But, behind every machine (read; software) is a human brain that programmes the machine.

AI is totally based on Human Intelligence (HI); a combination of Intelligence Quotient (IQ), Emotional Quotient, (EQ), Social Quotient (SQ) and Adversity Quotient (AQ). This paper advocates that AI does help in managing and fixing human error, leads to near accuracy and precision, zero risk index, round – the – clock availability and digital assistance, to list a few. But, the disadvantages are high costs, nil

creativity, and no scope for in – state improvements. One ought to be a 'slave' on the as - is - available software, till it is replaced by another software. Adversity Quotient (AQ) of AI is practically Nil except for 'Recovery Software'. What about a 'Technical Glitch'? What about the ethical considerations and challenges?

Reflective Issues with AI

Where was AI when Einstein wrote $e = mc^2$? Where was AI when Newton discovered the Three Laws of Motions? It was in the year 1950 that Alan Turing wrote a treatise titled 'Computer Machinery and Intelligence' based on test of machine intelligence; 'The Imitation Game'. The first AI program was written in 1951. It was in the 90s that AI took off as a scholarly discipline. Does it sound logical to announce that academic discoveries, before John McCarthy (Father of AI), would have been more solid and robust? When is a 'self – aware' AI going to take birth? In such a scenario, how is the Oscillating Brain going to act and react in an air of Vacillating AI Milieu? Will brain be influenced by the Vacillating AI Milieu? Will AI be impacted by the Oscillating Brain? Can we fit a biological brain into a machine via AL pathways? Can we fit in a machine into the brain (Musk - Model)?

In the Hollywood movie, 'A Beautiful Mind'; 2001, the main character (Nobel Laureate John Nash) is depicted as a human being mesmerized by codes and intricate patterns, itinerant in the region of lost in thinking and researching game theory that culminated in the famous 'Nash's Theorem'. Where was AI then? All researches of Nash are sans AI but HI. In Hollywood movie, 'Lucy'; 2014, Prof Norman (specialist in 'different human capabilities') experiments to access 100% of brain's abilities. Containing about 100 billion microscopic cells ('neurons'), this depicts 'evolution of (artificial) intelligence'. A thought-provoking investigation of human potential, as the brain capacity of Lucy

continues to increase; Lucy becomes increasingly disconnected from human form. In the Bollywood movie, *Enthiran / Machine*; (2010), a sophisticated android robot has been adopted as a replacement of human being via. 'Neural Schema'. Similar analogy can be drawn with chess events involving Boris Spassky, Gary Kasparov and Anatoly Karpov, to list a few.

Methodology

'There are no 'good' brains or 'bad' brains, only prepared and unprepared ones'.

..... Sweta Adatia (2024)

Methodology adopted is an interpretation of '*The Singularity Is Near*' by Ray Kurzweil (2005). Janet Maslin of The New York Times has commented that, 'mankind's technological knowledge has been snowballing, with dizzying prospects for the future.' Bill Gates has opined that, '*The Singularity Is Near* information technologies have advanced so far and fast that they enable humanity to transcend its biological limitations-transforming our lives in ways we can't yet imagine.'

Ray Kurzweil (2005) professes that 'The merging is the essence of the Singularity, an era in which our intelligence will become increasingly non-biological and trillions of times more powerful than it is today—the dawning of a new civilization that will enable us to transcend out biological limitations and amplify our creativity.' We contest this proposition. Rather we profess that our intelligence will become increasingly biological and trillions of times more powerful than AI via. EEG (electroencephalogram), QEEG (Quantitative electroencephalography), Loreta (mathematical approximation that measures activity of brain structures by calculating EEG and use it in neurofeedback), Slorete (standardized low-resolution brain electromagnetic tomography), ERP (Event-related Potentials or Evoked Potentials), fMRI (Functional magnetic resonance imaging or functional MRI) and eye tracking, to list a few. Brain

waves, found to be induced in AI Machines, are excellent 'Mother Boards' to depict neural behaviour. Solemnizing a 'marriage of neuroscience and technology, Neurologist Dr. Sweta Adatia (Second Author), in her seminal work, 'Limitless Brains' (2024), has argued that through neuro imaging techniques cognitive functions, emotional intelligence and problem solving capabilities ('own thinking pattern') exhibit the 'unlimited powers' of human brain over AI. The experiments on 'inner workings of the brain' do significantly depict the power of a human brain over AI, albeit AI being a conduit in such experiments.

'It will be a long time before AI completely takes over human intelligence. 'AI mixes a lot of data and puts it out. However, the brain has its sensory phenomenon — ability to smell, touch, see, feel, and, most importantly, the soft emotional aspects of it. It's too soon to say that AI is going to be even competing with human intelligence. Yes, it will take away all the mundane and repetitive tasks. But I don't think it will ever replace the human thought process.'

..... Sweta Adatia (2024)

'The growing dependence on technology can reduce brain activity, potentially leading to atrophy or decreased cognitive capacity. Keeping the brain stimulated is crucial for maintaining its health. Passive consumption, like mindlessly scrolling through social media, can lead to 'digital dementia', a condition characterized by cognitive decline due to overreliance on digital devices. This problem is exacerbated by factors like genetics, environ-brain toxins, stress, and inadequate sleep. The brain's glymphatic system, active during sleep, helps clear out toxins, and poor sleep disrupts this process, contributing to rising dementia rates' (Sweta Adatia ;2024).

You know, things are going to be really different!
... No, no, I mean really different!

..... Mark Miller

We do admit and accept the theory of Ray that human-created technology is accelerating and its powers are expanding at an exponential pace. The claim by Kurzweil that 'in this new world, there will be no clear distinction between human and machine, real reality and virtual reality is debatable. How can there be no clear distinction between human and machine, real reality and virtual reality? Seems to be a tall claim although a safe margin till the year 2045 (two decades from today) has been projected. How will parity be arrived at? And, proposition by Ray that, 'We will be able to assume different bodies and take on a range of personae at will. In practical terms, human aging and illness will be reversed; pollution will be stopped; world hunger and poverty will be solved' is contested with one small word, 'How'? Can human aging and illness be reversed? Human body has its own limitations as dictated by pollution, global warming and other aspects. Can world hunger and poverty be solved? These seem today blurred, foggy, distorted and unclear.

The Argument

AI should not affect the brain evolution. It should give us in fact more opportunities to develop the brain even better. Technology is always for you and you are not for technology. We cannot let the brain's be fired by the AI It's time to feel confident. We are a complex network of elements that work together, and we cannot separate them. Combining neurofeedback, biofeedback, and artificial intelligence to improve cognitive and emotional wellbeing demonstrates the potential of cutting-edge methodologies in improving our brain health. It's inspiring to see how their research is advancing our understanding of the brain and opening up new possibilities. Adapted Neurosciences are revolutionizing our understanding of the brain and its ability to change and adapt. We would rather profess that our intelligence will become increasingly biological and trillions of times more powerful than AI

via. EEG, QEEG, Loreta, Slorete, ERP, fMRI and eye tracking, to list a few.

"If the difficulty of a physiological problem is mathematical in nature, ten physiologists ignorant of mathematics will get precisely as far as one physiologist ignorant of mathematics."

..... Norman Weiner and Warren McCulloch (1934).

"Is AI all inclusive, is it dependable, and is it decidable? Neural Networks, the 'sweetheart of Computer Sciences', are the 'motorists' or 'driving force' behind contemporary AI systems (conduct of neural arrangement). They are modeled after human brain and mimic the 'Wired Brain' (rational calculus of ideas immanent in nervous action). A combination of AI and human brain dynamics is the 'Pillar' towards healthy management of human beings (mechanistic conjecture of mind). This includes brain scans, biological data, memory tests, machine learning algorithms and information (Prof. Kourtzi; 2023). AI does help in providing tailored interventions 'biological feedback mechanisms'. AI systems in healthcare is at present a grey area that wants much effort in illuminating questions like what should be done to set in motion from research to adaptation.

"People are smarter than today's computers because brain employs a basic computational architecture that is suited to deal with a central aspect of natural information processing tasks that people are so good at."

..... Edem Gold (2023).

Conclusion

Ray is of the opinion that 'rate of paradigm shift (technical innovation) is accelerating and growing exponentially'. We agree to that. The World is experiencing a flood of 'Techno-Revolution via. Techno-Innovation'. Human brain scanning is one of

these exponentially improving technologies. This too we agree as a complement to AI. Ray propounds the concept of ‘non-biological intelligence’ which is an amalgamation of AI, ML and bio – technology. We do not agree to the statement of Ray that ‘Biology has inherent limitation’. Whether some limitations are ‘inherent’ or ‘conditional’, does depend on present state of knowledge, together with technology.

Interaction between AI and human brain dynamics is a dynamic interdisciplinary field. How is the Oscillating Brain going to act and react in an air of Vacillating AI Milieu? Experiments prove that the oscillating brain will react accordingly in an air of Vacillating AI Milieu. In a globalizing world, individuals face chaotic conditions that call for adopting changing technologies and opportunities for strategic thinking. Emerging field of behavioural sciences offers conjecture and practice to understand this dimension. First step involves functionality of brain (waves). This involves objective, description and analysis of how brain works to depict understanding of biological basis of economic behaviour (Satpathy; 2023).

Will brain be influenced by the Vacillating AI Milieu? Yes. Will AI be impacted by the Oscillating Brain? Yes. Can we fit a biological brain into a machine via AL pathways? Yes. Can we fit in a machine into the brain (Musk - Model)? Yes.

But, conclusions are that AI is short – lived with a shelf - life and biological brain will reign supreme.

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